

SCALABLE PRODUCTION OF EPOXY BASED NANOCOMPOSITES AND HIERARCHICAL COMPOSITES WITH HIGH CNT LOADINGS

T.M. Herceg¹, M.S. Zainol Abidin¹, C. Delfour³, E.S. Greenhalgh¹, A. Bismarck^{1,4}, M.S.P. Shaffer^{1*}

¹Imperial College London, UK;

³Airbus and ICAM, Toulouse, France;

⁴Institute of Materials Chemistry and Research, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Vienna, Austria.

* Corresponding author (m.shaffer@imperial.ac.uk)

Keywords: *nanocomposite, hierarchical composite, carbon nanotube*

1 Introduction

Over the past decade carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been incorporated as reinforcement not only in metal, ceramic and polymeric matrices, [1] but also as an additional constituent in continuous fibre composites. [2] One of the major challenges has been to distribute and disperse high loading fractions of CNTs in nanocomposites (NCs) and hierarchical composites (HCs). Choosing a suitable processing route is critical to tailoring properties at the nanoscale, which will in turn determine how the material behaves in the bulk.

With regards to the relationship between material properties and micro or nanostructure, nanotube agglomerates have been shown to be detrimental to all nanocomposite properties. Traditional dispersion techniques such as simple stirring and sonication have produced good quality nanocomposites for low CNT loadings, but have been ineffective once the nanotube volume fraction is increased beyond a few percent. [3] Thus far, producing good quality composites with high CNT content has been achieved with techniques such as layer-by-layer (LBL) deposition [4], resin infiltration of buckypapers [5], drawing, aligning and stacking CNT sheets [6] or resin infusing continuous and aligned CNT forests [7]. The properties of these composites have been impressive with improvements of as much as 716% for Young's modulus and 160% for tensile strength [6]. However, these methods are not readily and cheaply scalable with existing polymer composite processing and manufacturing equipment to produce high

quantities of nanocomposite, and therefore are not routes by which this new class of material could be incorporated in commercial applications.

Shear mixing by three roll milling was first identified as a promising approach for dispersing CNTs in epoxy resins by Gojny. [8] Thostenson and Chou have successfully employed this technique to produce a nanocomposite that benefited from multifunctional (mechanical, electrical and thermal) enhancements with as much as 5wt% multi walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). [9] Rosca and Hoa also used three roll milling to disperse as much as 8wt% CNTs in epoxy and optimized processing parameters to maximise the electrical conductivity of the resulting nanocomposite. [10] Unfortunately, there are no reports as to the success of shear mixing nanocomposite with higher CNT loadings.

There are two principal routes to producing HCs: applying the nanoreinforcement to fibres or the matrix. The first has been extensively reviewed in [2]. Furthermore, in addition to sizing or grafting carbon fibres with CNTs, fibres have also been conferred nanostructure via activation and carbon aerogel (CAG) modification in a recent StoRAGE effort [11] to develop multifunctional structural composites. The CAG modification in particular has yielded impressive results with a 500-fold increase in surface area of the fibres. When combined with a polymeric electrolyte matrix, the resulting composite showed a doubling of in-plane shear strength, 5-fold improvement of in-plane shear modulus and 3.5 fold enhancement of the compressive modulus and strength.

Attempts to produce HCs by reinforcing the matrix with CNTs have been plagued by processing difficulties caused by the increased matrix viscosity and nanotube infiltration. Some groups [12-14] have tried manufacturing HCs by conventional methods such as resin transfer moulding (RTM) and resin film infusion (RFI), but using matrices containing more than 1wt% CNTs resulted in CNT agglomeration and partial impregnation of the continuous fibres. Chen adapted the drum winding technique directly from prepreg manufacturing and produced good quality HCs containing 1.5% CNTs by volume of matrix [15]; however, this method is limited to low CNT concentration as increasing the CNT loading would render the impregnation bath too viscous for successful impregnation. Yokozeki has demonstrated the capability to produce good quality HCs in terms of homogeneity, CNT dispersion and distribution as well as mechanical and multifunctional properties using a wet impregnation route. [16-18]

The addition of nanoreinforcement to continuous fibre composites has been shown to improve both in- and out-of-plane properties. Compression and flexural strength were improved by as much as 15% and 18%, respectively, when adding between 5 and 10wt% cup stacked CNTs to the resin of a carbon fibre composite. [19] As for matrix dominated material properties, adding 0.25wt% CNTs to carbon fibre-epoxy composite improved interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) by 27% [20]. Most impressively, Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness were enhanced by 100% and 28% improvements in, respectively, by adding 5wt% cup stacked CNTs to an epoxy matrix before impregnating unidirectional carbon fibre. [17] Aligned CNT forests can also be placed in the interlaminar region of a laminate before consolidation, resulting in ILSS, Mode I and Mode II fracture toughnesses improvements of 69%, 150% and 200%, respectively.[21, 22] However, this route does not provide nanoreinforcement to the intralaminar space.

This work is primarily concerned with developing a processing route that allows the manufacturing of NCs and HCs with higher CNT loadings than previously reported using scalable processes. If good CNTs distributions and dispersions are achieved and maintained throughout processing, the resulting composites should have improved properties even at high CNT loadings.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The raw materials were chosen so as to promote the development of a scalable process. To this end, Nanocyl NC7000 multiwall carbon nanotubes are both affordable (€120/kg in 2012) and produced in large quantities. When choosing a resin system, there were two considerations. The first was to upgrade the properties of a cheap resin so that it could be used for structural applications. The second was that the nanocomposite was to be employed in the production of hierarchical carbon fibre composite prepreg by wet powder impregnation. For these reasons EPIKOTE 1001 was chosen because it is a relatively inexpensive coating resin, it is solid at room temperature and it is not soluble in water. Although dicyandiamide (DICY) is water soluble, it was used in small enough proportions as the hardener that it was completely encapsulated by the resin. Hexcel AS4C-GP in 12k tows was chosen as the carbon fibre, an epoxy sized variant of the AS4 fibres that are popular in the composite industry for structural applications. The epoxy sizing not only makes the fibres more compatible with the epoxy based matrix, but also makes for easier handling and less fibre damage as they pass through the impregnation line.

2.2 NC processing

The resin and hardener were combined with 2.4, 4.8, 9, 13 and 20% CNTs by weight of the composite. Control samples were prepared without any CNTs. The raw materials were mixed using a co-rotating PRISM TSE 16 TC twin screw extruder (Thermo Scientific HAAKE, UK) at temperatures up to 125°C. The nanocomposite product was then ground into a powder using a cryogenic ball mill (Cryomill, Retsch UK).

The powder was consolidated in dogbone shaped compression moulds. The powder filled moulds were vacuum bagged in a fashion similar to bagging a composite for autoclaving. The moulds were heated to 125°C under vacuum to allow the powder to melt while the air was removed. Following a 30 minute dwell to allow for melt relaxation, 4 tons of pressure (Moore Presses, UK) was applied to the mould, followed by curing at 165°C for 1 hour. The samples were further post-cured at 165°C overnight without vacuum. The control sample was cured

following the same temperature profile, but in a vacuum oven and without a plunger.

2.3 HC manufacturing

HCs were manufactured using an adapted wet powder impregnation route (Figure 1). The impregnation slurry consisted of nanocomposites powder suspended in deionised water with the aid of Triton X-100 surfactant (Sigma Aldrich, UK). The proportions of the slurry components were initially taken as those used by Ho, but required adjustment to produce prepregs with ~55% fibre volume fraction (V_f) consistently.

The carbon fibre was pulled through the impregnation bath with a tension of 10 N and speed of 6-7 rpm. The drum winder was run for 30-35 revolutions before the tow leading onto the drum was cut, the prepreg was removed by cutting it across the length of the drum and it was unrolled from the drum onto a sheet of PTFE film to dry.

The prepregs were dried at ambient conditions as well as under vacuum. The volume fractions of the plies were estimated from the weight of the plies, the amount of fibre in the plies and the densities of the fibre and matrix. Removing the prepreg from the relatively small diameter winding drum induces out of plane waviness, which was removed by hot pressing each ply at 100°C and 1 ton of pressure.

Laminates were 18 ply stacks with those prepregs closest to 55% V_f in the middle and those with lower V_f at the extremities to allow for some matrix bleed. Stacked plies were debulked for 10-15 minutes in a vacuum table (Vacform Composites, UK) throughout the lay-up process. The number of plies was selected in order to obtain a laminate approximately 3 mm thick. The middle plies were offset +3°/-3° to prevent fibre nesting and separated by 25 µm thick PTFE film (Aerovac Umeco, UK) inserted 60 mm into the laminate to form a starter crack for the fracture toughness measurements. Curing was done as with the NCs, but always including a dwell to allow melt relaxation.

2.4 Physical characterization

The curing of the nanocomposite was investigated by DSC (TA Q2000 DSC, TA Instruments) of the powder. The onset and peak temperatures were measured from dynamic scans at 5°C/min using the Universal Analysis 2000 software. To ensure that samples were fully cured, scans were followed by a

fast dynamic scan at 20°C/min. Once a curing regime was established that ensured complete crosslinking, that regime was also applied to curing HCs.

NC and HC compositions were determined by thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) (PerkinElmer, UK) and acid digestion, respectively. Densities were measured with a pycnometer (Accupyc 1330, Micrometrics GmbH) and used in conjunction with the composition measurements to calculate void content.

The dispersion and distribution of the CNTs in the epoxy system as well as the CNT pull-out length were characterised by SEM from the fracture surfaces of the tensile samples. Fractured samples were mounted onto aluminium stubs and sputter coated with a 5 nm thick layer of chromium to prevent electron charging. The specimens with the highest CNT loading were sufficiently conductive and did not require sputter coating. Imaging was done using 5 kV accelerating voltage.

2.5 Mechanical testing

The NC dog bone samples were consolidated in a mould shaped according to ASTM D638 (Type V) and polished with rotary polishing machine to remove any surface imperfections present from the moulding process. Strain gauges (FLK-1-11, TML, Japan) were glued to the working region of the dog bones with cyanoacrylate before tensile testing in an Instron 4505 screw driven machine at a reduced speed of 0.5mm/min due to the brittle nature of the material. The fracture surfaces were visually inspected to initially determine whether any defects or voids were present and then imaged by SEM to observe any microscopic inhomogeneities that could explain inconsistent mechanical properties.

The Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the HC laminates was measured and calculated according to ASTM D5528. At least five 180 mm long and 20 mm wide specimens were cut from each laminate panel before aluminium loading blocks were bonded to the pre-cracked ends with Araldite 2010 epoxy. The test was performed in the dual cantilever beam (DCB) configuration using a screw driven Instron 4505 testing machine (Instron Corporation, UK) which recorded load and displacement. Each specimen was pre-loaded at 5mm/min to initiate the crack, unloaded at 5mm/min to the initial displacement and re-loaded at 1mm/min

to propagate the crack. Crack length was monitored with a camera and traveling stage device built in-house. Mode I fracture toughness was calculated using the corrected beam theory (CBT).

4 Results and discussion

4.1 NC physical properties

The cure acceleration effect is believed to be a result of the high thermal conductivity of the CNTs coupled with their high aspect ratio [23]. Figure 2 shows typical curing exotherms from dynamic scans weighted to the mass of epoxy. The temperatures at the onset and peak of the curing reaction as measured from the dynamic scans are summarised in Table 1. The onset temperature decreases with increasing nanotube content, suggesting that the CNTs do initially accelerate the rate of curing. However, the temperature of the exotherm maximum does not vary significantly with CNT concentration. As the nanotube loading is increased the rate of reaction is initially accelerated, but increasing the CNT loading will cause the CNTs to impinge on the growing crosslinked structure, slowing the reaction rate as it approached the exotherm maximum.

TGA of fragments cut from the dogbone grips was used to calculate weight percentages of CNTs in the nanocomposites that were 0.8-1.6wt% below those expected based on the proportions of constituents measured out before extrusion (Table 2). The mass loss can be attributed to a combination of CNTs being removed by the air extraction unit during the feeding of the pre-mix into the extruder and TGA measurement variability. Nonetheless, to the knowledge of the authors an 18.4% CNT weight fraction in thermosetting nanocomposite is the highest achieved through a shear mixing process.

The volume fractions calculated from the measured weight fractions were used in a simple rule of mixtures (Equation 1) to calculate the projected nanocomposite density assuming complete consolidation and zero voids. The density values measured with a pycnometer were compared to those calculated from the rule of mixtures and found to be slightly lower suggesting that complete consolidation had not been achieved and the nanocomposites contained some porosity; however, quantitative analysis revealed that voids, in fact,

occupy less than 1% of the sample volume (Figure 3).

$$\rho_{NC} = \rho_{CNT}V_{f,CNT} + \rho_{matrix}(1 - V_{f,CNT}) \quad (1)$$

For the type of CNTs used in this study agglomerates are typically a few micrometers in diameter and spaced 10-30 μm apart. [10] As evident in Figure 4, CNTs were not observed to have concentrated in agglomerates and, for the most part, even appeared to be individualised (Figure 5). Although proving promising, mechanical shearing in general has only been utilised as a means of producing nanocomposites with nanotube weight fractions of a few percent. The addition of nanotubes has been shown to dramatically increase matrix viscosity [24], creating high shear forces and heat, which could induce thermosetting matrices to crosslink and damage the mixing equipment. However, careful control of speed, torque and temperature has allowed excellent dispersion and distribution of high CNT loading fractions in epoxies.

4.2 HC physical properties

From visual examination of the prepregs, the impregnation appeared successful. Drying the prepreg overnight at ambient conditions allowed the majority of the water to evaporate. The resulting sheets were rigid, suggesting that the matrix particles had wet the carbon fibres, holding the tows together (Figure 6). Microscopic powder particles and macroscopic powder clusters could be observed on the surface (Figure 7). The clusters, in particular, reached dimensions on the order of a few hundred micrometers, sufficiently large to disturb fibre alignment and thus negatively impact compression performance. More worryingly, the large CNT loading in the powder particles renders them elastic, reducing the extent of matrix flow during consolidation, a process which tends to make a laminate more homogenous. The estimated V_f of the plies calculated ranged from 40 to 65%. Although the values were only a rough estimate they proved useful in ranking the prepregs so that those with V_f closest to 55% could be placed closest to the interlaminar region.

The fibre and void volume fractions of the laminates are summarized in Table 3. The V_f of the laminates

were surprisingly close to the target value of 55% considering the novelty of the manufacturing procedure. The void fractions in the baseline laminate and the one containing 2vol% CNTs are encouragingly low and are evidence that the material was indeed sufficiently consolidated. The higher void content of the HC with the higher CNT loading suggests that the large amount of CNTs in the matrix drastically increased its viscosity, leading to less successful consolidation. Based on the calculated volume fractions it was also determined that the overall CNT volume fractions in the HCs were 2.0 and 5.5%. The highest reported CNT loading in an HC was 12% by weight of matrix [18]; the HC with the highest CNT loading manufactured through the process presented here contains 50% more CNTs.

4.3 NC mechanical properties

The values for the Young's moduli measured from the tensile tests are summarised in Figure 8. In all previous studies of nanocomposites with randomly dispersed CNTs the authors observed an improvement in Young's modulus up to CNT loadings of a few volume percent, after which modulus values deteriorated due to nanotube agglomerations resulting from ineffective processing. [25] In this work, good nanotube dispersion and distribution were maintained through the processing to the consolidated nanocomposite due to the processing route developed and short nanotubes used, allowing Young's modulus to increase monotonically with increasing CNT volume fraction (Figure 8). Nanotube percolation affects the nanocomposite Young's modulus with the reinforcement efficiency ($\delta E/\delta V_f$) visibly decreasing around 2vol%. Mechanistically, the efficiency reduction is expected due to a smaller fraction of nanotubes active in stress transfer. [26] Since it has been shown that adding only 1wt% of randomly dispersed MWCNTs can double the Young's modulus of an epoxy resin [27], one would expect that adding 18.4wt% CNTs would enhance the stiffness tremendously; however, the improvement of only 82% observed in this work suggests that nanocomposites containing short, defective and percolating CNTs will exhibit relatively low reinforcement efficiencies.

Unlike the Young's modulus, the nanocomposite strength does not increase monotonically (Figure 8).

As apparent from Figure 9, the neat resin and nanocomposites with low CNT loading fractions exhibit plasticity, but as the CNTs formed a percolating network the material was embrittled, reducing the maximum strain and causing it to fail elastically. This phenomenon is reflected in the strength non-linearity around the electrical percolation threshold. In addition to CNT percolation, the microstructural heterogeneity can also adversely impact nanocomposite strength due to inefficient load transfer; material strength could be further increased by ensuring better homogeneity, particularly for high CNT loadings.

4.4 HC mechanical properties

Typical R-curves from the DCB test are shown in Figure 10. Both the control composite and HCs are well behaved in the Mode I test with the G_{Ic} values rising after initiation through a matrix rich pocket and remaining flat throughout crack propagation. The falling R-curve behaviour typical for cracks propagating interlaminarly through unidirectional composites was not observed because there was a small degree of fibre bridging.

The initiation and propagation values for the baseline composite are high relative to those typically measured for carbon fibre-thermosetting resin laminates (100-200 J/m² [28]). The large molecular weight of the resin that makes it solid at ambient temperatures and thus attractive for this processing route also gives it a high fracture toughness. The addition of 2.0vol% CNTs enhances the initiation and propagation G_{Ic} values by 24% and 20%, respectively. For both the baseline composite and the HC the standard deviations are less than 10% of the toughness values averaged from at least five specimens, suggesting that the laminate panels did not contain macroscopic inhomogeneities. The average fracture toughness values of the HC containing 5.5vol% CNTs are nearly identical to those of the baseline composite, although the standard deviations were as high as 20% of the average values. The lower fracture toughness relative to the HCs containing 2.0vol% CNTs is attributed primarily to the higher void content (2.7 ± 1.7), which does not provide any fracture resistance.

5. Conclusions and outlook

A powder based processing route was developed, allowing manufacturing of epoxy nanocomposites with up to 18.4wt% randomly aligned, but well distributed and dispersed MWNTs. Furthermore, the nanocomposite powder and carbon fibre were employed as constituents in a wet powder impregnation process to produce hierarchical composite containing up to 5.5vol% CNTs. Characterisation of these materials has shown that they can be successfully consolidated and that the addition of nanoreinforcement enhances mechanical properties. The processing is being further modified by reducing the powder particle size to reduce the extent of resin and nano-filler segregation and further enhance composite performance by accessing more of the nanotubes' potential.

Figure 1. Schematic of the wet powder impregnation drum winding line used to produce prepreg.

Figure 2. Dynamic DSC scans of NCs.

Table 1. Onset and peak curing temperatures from dynamic DSC scans of NCs.

wt% CNT	Curing onset (°C)	Exotherm max (°C)
0	173	188
1.2	168	187
3.5	167	187
8.3	162	188
12.2	163	186
18.4	156	186

Table 2. Weight and volume fractions of CNTs in NCs.

wt% CNT expected	wt% CNT measured	vol% CNT measured
0	0	0
2.4	1.2	0.7
4.8	3.5	2.1
9.1	8.3	4.9
13	12.2	7.4
20	18.4	11.5

Figure 3. Void fractions in NCs as determined from pycnometry and rule of mixtures calculation.

Figure 4. Low (left) and high (right) magnification SEM micrographs of nanocomposite showing dispersion and distribution of nanotubes.

Figure 5. SEM of individual CNT.

Figure 7. Optical micrograph of prepreg manufactured with nanocomposite powder containing 11.5vol% CNTs.

Figure 6. Impregnated prepreg sheet after drying and hot pressing.

Table 3. Fibre and void volume fractions as measured by acid digestion of laminates with varying CNT loadings.

CNT vol. fraction in matrix (%)	CNT vol. fraction in composite (%)	V _f (%)	Void vol. fraction (%)
0	0	55.±0.6	0.6±0.2
4.9	2.0	58.8±0.7	0
11.5	5.5	49.7±0.9	2.7±1.7

Figure 8. Young's modulus and strength values from tensile tests of NCs.

Figure 9. Stress-strain response from tensile testing of nanocomposites.

Figure 10. Typical R-curve from DCB testing of HCs.

References

- Harris, P.J.F., *Carbon nanotube composites*. International Materials Reviews, 2004. **49**(1): p. 31-43.
- Qian, H., et al., *Carbon nanotube-based hierarchical composites: a review*. Journal of Materials Chemistry, 2010. **20**(23): p. 4751-4762.
- Guadagno, L., et al., *Mechanical and barrier properties of epoxy resin filled with multi-walled carbon nanotubes*. Carbon, 2009. **47**(10): p. 2419-2430.
- Feng, Q.P., et al., *Synthesis of carbon nanotube/epoxy composite films with a high nanotube loading by a mixed-curing-agent assisted layer-by-layer method and their electrical conductivity*. Carbon, 2010. **48**(7): p. 2057-2062.
- Spitalsky, Z., et al., *High volume fraction carbon nanotube-epoxy composites*. Nanotechnology, 2009. **20**(40): p. -.
- Cheng, Q.F., et al., *Carbon nanotube/epoxy composites fabricated by resin transfer molding*. Carbon, 2010. **48**(1): p. 260-266.
- Cebeci, H., et al., *Multifunctional properties of high volume fraction aligned carbon nanotube polymer composites with controlled morphology*. Composites Science and Technology, 2009. **69**(15-16): p. 2649-2656.
- Gojny, F.H., et al., *Carbon nanotube-reinforced epoxy-compo sites: enhanced stiffness and fracture toughness at low nanotube content*. Composites Science and Technology, 2004. **64**(15): p. 2363-2371.
- Thostenson, E.T. and T.W. Chou, *Processing-structure-multi-functional property relationship in carbon nanotube/epoxy composites*. Carbon, 2006. **44**(14): p. 3022-3029.
- Rosca, I.D. and S.V. Hoa, *Highly conductive multiwall carbon nanotube and epoxy composites produced by three-roll milling*. Carbon, 2009. **47**(8): p. 1958-1968.
- E.S. Greenhalgh, J.A., L.E. Asp, A. Bismarck, Q.P.V Fontana, M. Houle, G. Kalinka, A. Kucernak, M. Mistry, S. Nguyen, H. Qian, M.S.P. Shaffer, N. Shirshova, J.H.G. Steinke, M. Weinrich, *Mechanical and microstructural characterisation of multifunctional structural power composites*, in ICCM 192013: Montreal.
- Gojny, F.H., et al., *Influence of nano-modification on the mechanical and electrical properties of conventional fibre-reinforced composites*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2005. **36**(11): p. 1525-1535.
- Fan, Z.H., K.T. Hsiao, and S.G. Advani, *Experimental investigation of dispersion during flow of multi-walled carbon nanotube/polymer suspension in fibrous porous media*. Carbon, 2004. **42**(4): p. 871-876.

14. Sadeghian, R., et al., *Manufacturing carbon nanofibers toughened polyester/glass fiber composites using vacuum assisted resin transfer molding for enhancing the mode-I delamination resistance*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2006. **37**(10): p. 1787-1795.
15. Chen, W., et al., *Basalt fiber-epoxy laminates with functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2009. **40**(8): p. 1082-1089.
16. Yokozeki, T., et al., *Mechanical properties of CFRP laminates manufactured from unidirectional prepregs using CSCNT-dispersed epoxy*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2007. **38**(10): p. 2121-2130.
17. Yokozeki, T., et al., *Fracture toughness improvement of CFRP laminates by dispersion of cup-stacked carbon nanotubes*. Composites Science and Technology, 2009. **69**(14): p. 2268-2273.
18. Yokozeki, T., Y. Iwahori, and S. Ishiwata, *Matrix cracking behaviors in carbon fiber/epoxy laminates filled with cup-stacked carbon nanotubes (CSCNTs)*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2007. **38**(3): p. 917-924.
19. Iwahori, Y., et al., *Mechanical properties improvements in two-phase and three-phase composites using carbon nano-fiber dispersed resin*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2005. **36**(10): p. 1430-1439.
20. Bekyarova, E., et al., *Multiscale carbon nanotube-carbon fiber reinforcement for advanced epoxy composites*. Langmuir, 2007. **23**(7): p. 3970-3974.
21. Garcia, E.J., et al., *Fabrication and multifunctional properties of a hybrid laminate with aligned carbon nanotubes grown In Situ*. Composites Science and Technology, 2008. **68**(9): p. 2034-2041.
22. Garcia, E.J., B.L. Wardle, and A.J. Hart, *Joining prepreg composite interfaces with aligned carbon nanotubes*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2008. **39**(6): p. 1065-1070.
23. Puglia, D., L. Valentini, and J.M. Kenny, *Analysis of the cure reaction of carbon nanotubes/epoxy resin composites through thermal analysis and Raman spectroscopy*. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 2003. **88**(2): p. 452-458.
24. Shaffer, M.S.P., X. Fan, and A.H. Windle, *Dispersion and packing of carbon nanotubes*. Carbon, 1998. **36**(11): p. 1603-1612.
25. Coleman, J.N., et al., *Small but strong: A review of the mechanical properties of carbon nanotube-polymer composites*. Carbon, 2006. **44**(9): p. 1624-1652.
26. Ouali, N., J.Y. Cavaille, and J. Perez, *Elastic, Viscoelastic and Plastic Behavior of Multiphase Polymer Blends*. Plastics Rubber and Composites Processing and Applications, 1991. **16**(1): p. 55-60.
27. Bai, J., *Evidence of the reinforcement role of chemical vapour deposition multi-walled carbon nanotubes in a polymer matrix*. Carbon, 2003. **41**(6): p. 1325-1328.
28. Hodgkinson, J.M., *Mechanical testing of advanced fibre composites* 2000, Cambridge: CRC Press; Woodhead. xv, 362 p.